

Synthesis of Phenolic Schiff Bases and their Reaction with DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ System

P. D. LOKHANDE and B. J. GHIYA*

Chemistry Department, Institute of Science,
Nagpur-440 001

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SCHIFF bases exhibit anticancer and antitubercular activities¹. Anticancer Schiff bases have been synthesised by condensation of aniline with substituted benzaldehydes². Benzisoxazoles are known for their biological activities³. Benzoxazoles were prepared by cyclisation of O,N-diacetyl derivative *o*-aminophenol at lower temperature; by heating *o*-aminophenol with carboxylic acid or its derivative⁴ or by the action of KNH₂ in liquid ammonia on aroyl derivative of both *o*- or *m*-chloroaniline via *o*-hydroxyphenylamide. Benzisoxazole are reported⁵ to be formed by heating *o*-bromobenzophenone oximes and acetophenone oxime acetate. 3-Phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin with hydroxylamine hydrochloride gives 1,2-benzisoxazole-3-phenylacetic acid⁶. 2-Hydroxychalcone oxime on stirring with silica-gel in ethylenedichloride is reported to give 3-styrylbenzisoxazole⁷, and 2-hydroxydibenzoylmethane with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in DMF-water gives 1,2-benzisoxazole⁸. Phenolic Schiff bases on oxidative cyclisation by Ag₂O and CuCl₂ in nitrobenzene give benzoxazole⁹.

In the present communication, we report the synthesis of 1,2-benzisoxazole and benzoxazole by oxidative cyclisation of phenolic Schiff bases with DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ system. DMSO-I₂ with or without H₂SO₄ reagents has been used for oxidative cyclisation of 2'-hydroxychalcone to flavone and dehydrogenation to flavonoids¹⁰. It was thought of interest to study the oxidative cyclisation by DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ of 2-hydroxybenzylideneaniline and 2-hydroxyaniline benzylidene. Phenolic Schiff bases 1 were synthesised by condensing 2-aminophenol and substituted benzaldehydes and 2 were synthesised by condensing 2-hydroxyacetophenone and salicylaldehyde separately with substituted aniline in presence of a drop of H₂SO₄ or acetic acid in ethanol medium. Schiff bases 1 with DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ gave 3 in good yield and gave no colouration with ferric chloride. Spectral study and elemental analysis suggest 3 to be a dimer (Scheme 1).

Phenolic Schiff bases 2 with DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ gave a white solid 4 which showed negative ferric

1,3a; R=H
b; R=OCH₃,
c; R=NO₂,
Scheme 1

chloride test indicating involvement of phenolic hydroxyl group in cyclisation. Its spectra showed λ_{max} at 342, 328 nm and ν_{max} at 1 700, 1 600 cm⁻¹ and other peaks. Compound 4 was given the structure as *N*-phenylbenzisoxazolone (Scheme 2).

2,4a; X=CH₃, R'=CH₃, R''=OCH₃,
b; X=CH₃, R'=Cl, R''=OCH₃,
c; X=H, R'=H, R''=H
d; X=H, R'=H, R''=OCH₃,
Scheme 2

Experimental

Benzylidene-2-hydroxyaniline (1): A mixture of *o*-aminophenol (0.1 mol) and substituted benzaldehyde (0.12 mol) dissolved in ethanol (120 ml) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (2–3 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for 30 min. It was then cooled and diluted with ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from 40% ethanol: 1a (70%), m.p. 98°; 1b (80%), 78°; 1c (95%), 118°.

2-Hydroxybenzylidene aniline (2): A mixture of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 mol) and aniline (or anisidine, toluidines etc.) dissolved in ethanol (100 ml) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (2–3 drops), was refluxed for 30 min. It was then cooled, diluted

with ice-cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from 40% ethanol. Similarly, other Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of salicylaldehyde and anilines : **2a** (70%), m. p. 126° ; **2b** (80%), 131° ; **2c** (60%), 40° ; **2d** (60%), 80°.

Action of DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ on 1 : A mixture of phenolic Schiff bases (**1** ; 0.01 mol) dissolved in dimethylsulphoxide (40 ml) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (1 drop) was refluxed for 10 min. It was then cooled and a little catalytic amount of iodine was added. The reaction mixture was again heated for 1 h on a water-bath, then cooled and diluted with ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water, 10% sodium thiosulphate solution (to remove iodine) and again by water and crystallised from alcohol : **3a-c** (90%), m. p. 300°.

Reaction of 2 with DMSO-I₂-H₂SO₄ system : A mixture of **2** (X=H or CH₃ ; 0.01 mol) dissolved in DMSO (40 ml) and H₂SO₄ (1 drop) was refluxed for 10 min and then a small crystal of iodine (catalytic amount) was added. It was again heated on a water-bath for 1 h, then cooled, diluted with cold water, filtered, and the solid was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (10%) and water and crystallised from ethanol : **4a** (40%), m. p. 155° ; **4b** (60%), 138° ; **4c** (40%), 62° ; **4d** (75%), 84°.

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